

pyteealca - A Python-based Life Cycle Assessment Tool

pyteea-lca is an object-oriented Python repository designed to integrate process simulation data (e.g., from Aspen Plus®) with datasets from Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) databases like [ecoinvent](#), facilitating a seamless and automated workflow from simulation data to life cycle impact assessment results. The library supports linking simulation data with LCA datasets, writing and storing data in [brightway2](#) format and computing LCA results with life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methods.

The library is designed as the core analysis layer within a modular toolbox ecosystem. It integrates process simulation data, LCA databases, and robust unit handling to enable reproducible, data-driven, and configurable life cycle assessments.

Key Features

- Standards-based LCA methodology following ISO 14040/14044
- Multiple data sources for process information:
 - Direct coupling to Aspen Plus® simulations via `aspenparserDLR`
 - Structured JSON, YAML, or CSV input data
- Configurable analysis setup using structured configuration files for settings
- Consistent unit handling and conversion via `pyteeauc`
- Linkage of process information data with LCA datasets
- Sensitivity analysis for specific linkage groups
- Export option of LCI into `brightway2`
- Saving option for life cycle inventories and LCIA scores of linked LCA datasets for faster reruns
- Object-oriented and extensible design, enabling customization and integration into larger workflows

Requirements

The tool requires the three in-house repositories [aspenparserDLR](#), and [pyteeauc](#). Their required version together with additionally required publicly available libraries are listed below.

```
dependencies = [  
    "aspenparserDLR @ git+https://.../aspenparserdlr.git@0.2.13",  
    "pyteeauc @ git+https://.../pyteeauc.git@0.1.2",  
    "numpy>=1.24.3",  
    "loguru>=0.6.0",
```

```
"pandas>=2.0.1",
"psutil>=5.9.5",
"pydantic>=2.6.2",
"pywin32>=304",
"pytest>=7.3.1",
"pytz>=2022.6",
"PyYAML>=6.0",
"pyside6>=6.7.0",
"kaleido>=0.2.1",
"plotly>=5.19.0",
"brightway2>=2.4.6"
]
```

```
requires-python = ">=3.10"
```

Configure the project

Set the file locations

Provide the file paths to your simulation information, selected impact categories, linked block / stream files, and data sources to use as input. Additionally, you can provide additional linked files, and lci and lcia data from previous assessments.

```
# Overview of file locations for pyteea-lca
```

```
config_version: 0.3.0
```

```
config_type: LCAInputConfig
```

```
simulation_obj_file: ..\input_files\simulation_obj_list.yml #
available after running `extract data from aspen simulation`
```

```
simulation_units_file: ..\input_files\simulation_units.yml #
Optional, available after running `extract data from aspen simulation`
```

```
simulation_components_file: ..\input_files\component_list.yml #
Optional, available after running `extract data from aspen simulation`
```

```
lci_impact_categories: ..\input_files\lci_impact_categories.yml #
List of impact categories to be evaluated
```

```
linked_block_files:
```

- ..\linked_files\linked_block_objects-ap.yml
- ..\linked_files\linked_block_objects-yml.yml

```
linked_stream_files:
```

- ..\linked_files\linked_stream_objects-ap.yml
- ..\linked_files\linked_stream_objects-json.yml

```

linked_additional_files:
  - ..\linked_files\linked_additional_objects.yml #
    Optional

lci_data: ..\results\interim\lci_data_project_process_name_V1.csv #
    Optional

lcia_data: ..\results\interim\lcia_data_project_process_name_V1.csv #
    Optional

lca_config_file: lca_config.yml

results_path: ..\results

data_sources:
  - source_id: aspen_file_input
    data_type: aspenplus
    path: ..\bkg_file\example_process.bkg
  - source_id: yaml_file_input
    data_type: yaml
    path: ..\input_files\yaml_file_input.yml
  - source_id: json_testing
    data_type: json
    path: ..\input_files\json_file_input.json

```

Set up LCA configuration file

Change values and figures as required for the desired life cycle assessment.

File containing all the relevant information for performing an LCA

```

config_version: 0.2.0

config_type: BasicLCAConfig

project: BioSAF # bw project name

database_name: Case 1.1 # name for database to be created

process_name: SAF production # name for process

location: GLO # Country code for process

product_stream:
  name: SAF
  source_id: aspen_file_input # source_id of data source for
    product stream
  stream_id: PRODUCT # name of the stream in the given
    source

functional_unit:
  value: 1
  unit: kg # weight / volume / energy unit

```

```

eval_settings:
  lci:
    True # write life cycle inventory
         (LCI) to brightway
  lcia: True # perform life cycle impact
           assessment (LCIA) for product stream
  export_lci: True # exporting LCI to given
                 results_path
  export_lcia_interim: False # exporting LCIA data of linked
                             exchanges to given results_path
  export_lcia_results: True # exporting LCIA results to given
                            results_path

```

Define LCIA impact categories

- ('IPCC 2021', 'climate change', 'GWP 100a')
- ('EF v3.1', 'acidification', 'accumulated exceedance (AE)')

Load simulation data

- Directly via the aspenparserDLR repository for AspenPlus integration.

```

from pathlib import Path
from aspenparserDLR import aspen_main as am

aspenparser_config = Path(r'config_files/aspenparserDLR_config.yml')
am.export_full_sim_data(aspenparser_config)

```

- From pre-exported or created .json, .csv, .yaml files.

Link simulation objects with LCA datasets

Link simulation data with LCA databases by either using the provided graphical user interface or editing the linked files manually.

Link simulation blocks

```

from pathlib import Path
from pyteecalca import lca_link_objects as link_objects
from pyteecalca import ui_link_blocks_and_db_bw as linkblocks

lca_file_loc = Path(r'config_files/lca_file_locations_test.yml')
lca_files = link_objects.read_lca_loc_file(lca_file_loc)
linkblocks.link_blocks(lca_files)

```

Exemplary linked blocks file

```
config_version: 0.2.1
config_type: LinkedBlocks
source_id: aspen_file_input
data_type: aspenplus
links:
- aspen_id: COMPR-1
  sim_prop: wnet
  process_step: Upgrading
  exchange_id: ('ecoinvent-3.11-cutoff',
                '6a5a47c4e8485c587c8dec6934feabae')
  factor: null
  group_id:
    Compressor # Unique id required for sensitivity study, can be
    left empty otherwise
- aspen_id: HEATER
  sim_prop: qcalc
  process_step: Gas cleaning
  exchange_id: ('ecoinvent-3.11-cutoff',
                'eff116d808e7e5e284209d05c3be2307')
  factor:
    - value: 1/50000
      unit: 1/h
    - value: 20
      unit: a
    - value: 8000
      unit: h/a
  group_id: Heater
```

Link simulation streams

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteecalca import lca_link_objects as link_objects
from pyteecalca import ui_link_streams_and_db_bw as linkstreams

lca_file_loc = Path(r'config_files/lca_file_locations_test.yml')
lca_files = link_objects.read_lca_loc_file(lca_file_loc)
linkstreams.link_streams(lca_files)
```

Exemplary linked streams file

```
config_version: 0.2.0
config_type: LinkedStreams
source_id: aspen_file_input
data_type: aspenplus
links:
- aspen_id: COLD-IN
  component: H2O
  process_step: Steam cycle
```


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